

Studies on imidazolinone derivatives : synthesis and antimicrobial activity of 1-[2(1*H*)-quinoxalinon-1'-ylacetamido]-2-phenyl/methyl-4-arylidene-5-oxoimidazolines

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Some new 4-substituted-benzylidene-1-[2(1*H*)-quinoxalinon-1'-ylacetamido]-2-phenyl/methyl-4-arylidene-5-oxoimidazolines have been prepared by reacting 2-oxaquinoxalin-1-ylacetylhydrazine with preformed azlactones. The compounds are screened for antibacterial and antifungal activities.

Imidazolinones¹ and quinoxalines² possess diversified biological activities. With a view to assessing the potential of imidazolinones and quinoxaline moieties, some new 4-substituted-benzylidene-1-[2(1*H*)-quinoxalinon-1'-ylacetamido]-2-phenyl/methyl-4-arylidene-5-oxoimidazolines (3) have been synthesized by the action of various types of azlactones (2), which were obtained by the condensation of glycine with different aromatic aldehydes in presence of sodium acetate and acetic anhydride, on 2-oxaquinoxalin-1-ylacetylhydrazine (1). The structure of the compounds (3) were assigned on the basis of elemental analyses and IR and ¹H NMR and/or mass spectral data of two representative compounds, viz. 3i and 3i'. The products were screened for their antimicrobial activity against different strains of bacteria and fungi.

All the compounds were screened for their antimicrobial activity by cup-plate method³ at a concentration of 50 µg against gram-positive bacteria like *B. megaterium* and *S. citrus* and gram-negative bacteria like *E. coli* and *S. typhosa*, and fungal strain *A. niger*. Most of the compounds were found moderately active against different strains of bacteria. The maximum activity was observed in imidazolinone derivatives (zone of inhibition in mm) : R = 4-hydroxy-3-methoxyphenyl (11–14), phenyl (11–15), 4-methoxyphenyl (12–16), 2-furyl (13–16) substituents against *E. coli*, *S. citrus* and *A. niger*.

Experimental

M.ps. were determined by open capillary method and are uncorrected. IR spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Shimadzu IR-435 spectrophotometer, mass spectra on a JEOL 300 spectrometer (70 eV) and PMR spectra on Hitachi R-1200 spectrometer.

2,3a-n X = C₆H₅

- R
- a 2-Cl.C₆H₄
 - b 4-Cl.C₆H₄
 - c -CH=CH.C₆H₅
 - d 3,4-(OCH₃)₂.C₆H₃
 - e 2-OH.C₆H₄
 - f 3-OH.C₆H₄
 - g 4-OH.C₆H₄
 - h 4-OH, 3-OCH₃.C₆H₃
 - i 2-OCH₃.C₆H₄
 - j 4-OCH₃.C₆H₄
 - k 3-NO₂.C₆H₄
 - l 4-NO₂.C₆H₄
 - m 2-Furyl
 - n 2-NO₂.C₆H₄

2,3a'-n' X = CH₃

- R
- a' 2-Cl.C₆H₄
 - b' 4-Cl.C₆H₄
 - c' -CH=CH.C₆H₅
 - d' 3,4-(OCH₃)₂.C₆H₃
 - e' 2-OH.C₆H₄
 - f' 3-OH.C₆H₄
 - g' 4-OH.C₆H₄
 - h' 4-OH, 3-OCH₃.C₆H₃
 - i' 2-OCH₃.C₆H₄
 - j' 4-OCH₃.C₆H₄
 - k' 3-NO₂.C₆H₄
 - l' 4-NO₂.C₆H₄
 - m' C₆H₅
 - n' 3,4-Cl₂.C₆H₃

2(1*H*)-Quinoxalinon-1-ylacetylhydrazine (1) : A mixture of ethyl [2(1*H*)-quinoxalinon-yl]acetate³ (5 g, 0.024 mol) and excess of hydrazine hydrate (2.25 ml, 0.048 mol) in absolute ethanol was refluxed for 3 h. The reaction mixture was then cooled to room temperature and the resulting

solid was crystallized from water, 66%, m.p. 205°; ν_{\max} 3500–3400 (NH₂NH), 1680, 1685 (C=O), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N).

4-o-Methoxyphenylidene-1-[2(1H)-quinoxalinon-1'-ylacetamido]-2-methyl/phenyl-5-oxoimidazolines (3a-m): Acetyl, benzoylglycine and 4-substituted-arylidene-2-methyl/phenyl-5-oxazolones were prepared by reported methods⁴. A mixture of **1** (1.5 g, 0.006 mol) and 2-methyl/phenyl-4-(2'-methoxyphenylidene)-5-oxazolone (0.006 mol) was refluxed in pyridine for 3 h. The resulting mass was poured onto crushed ice and neutralized with HCl, filtered and the solid was crystallized from methanol: **3i** (75.13%), m.p. 135° (Found: C, 69.90; H, 4.50; N, 15.09. C₂₇H₂₁O₄N₅ requires: C, 67.64; H, 4.38; N, 14.61%) ν_{\max} 3400 (NH), 1680 (C=O for quinoxaline moiety), 1700 (C=O for imidazolinone moiety), 1605 cm⁻¹ (C=N); m/z 479 (M⁺), 187 (100%), 159 (44), 131 (45), 105 (25); **3i'** (54%), m.p. 187° (Found: C, 65.81; H, 4.89; N, 17.40. C₂₂H₁₉O₄N₅ requires: C, 63.53; H, 4.55; N, 16.78%); ν_{\max} 3450 (NH), 1680 (C=O for quinoxaline moiety), 1705 (C=O), 1600 cm⁻¹ (C=N); ¹H NMR (CDCl₃) δ 2.85 (3H, s, CH₃), 3.75 (3H, s, OCH₃), 5.0 (2H, s, CH₂), 5.2 (1H, s, CH), 6.8–7.2 (9H, m, ArH); m/z 417 (M⁺), 187 (100%), 159, 131, 77.

Similarly, other substituted imidazolinones were condensed with different azlactones to yield the products: **3a**, m.p. 158°; **b**; 145°; **c**, 175°; **d**, 235°; **e**, 170°; **f**, 185°; **g**, 175°; **h**, 165–170°; **j**, 140°; **k**, 196°; **l**, 190°; **m**, 210°; **n**, 197°; **3a'**, 125°; **b'**, 190°; **c'**, 185°; **d'**, 199°; **e'**, 165°; **f'**, 180°; **g'**, 167°; **h'**, 210°; **j'**, 205°; **k'**, 85°; **l'**, 210°; **m'**, 176°; **n'**, 98°.

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